

References

- [1] Gonalo Baptista and Tiago Oliveira. 2019. Gamification and serious games: A literature meta-analysis and integrative model. *Computers in Human Behavior* 92 (2019), 306–315. doi:10.1016/j.chb.2018.11.030
- [2] Elizabeth A. Boyle, Thomas Hainey, Thomas M. Connolly, Grant Gray, Jeffrey Earp, Michela Ott, Theodore Lim, Manuel Ninaus, Claudia Ribeiro, and Joao Pereira. 2016. An update to the systematic literature review of empirical evidence of the impacts and outcomes of computer games and serious games. *Computers & Education* 94 (2016), 178–192. doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2015.11.003
- [3] Vern L Bullough and Bonnie Bullough. 2021. *The care of the sick: The emergence of modern nursing*. Routledge.
- [4] Byron Castillo-Parra, Brigitte Hidalgo-Cajo, Maria Vasquez-Barrera, and Jose Oleas-Lopez. 2022. Gamification in higher education: A review of the literature. *World Journal on Educational Technology: Current Issues* 14, 3, 797–816. doi:10.18844/wjet.v14i3.7341
- [5] Thomas M. Connolly, Elizabeth A. Boyle, Ewan MacArthur, Thomas Hainey, and James M. Boyle. 2012. A systematic literature review of empirical evidence on computer games and serious games. *Computers & Education* 59, 2 (2012), 661–686. doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2012.03.004
- [6] Cambridge Academic Content Dictionary. 2025. Medicine. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/medicine>
- [7] Stefan HE Kaufmann. 2019. Immunology's coming of age. *Frontiers in immunology* 10 (2019), 684.
- [8] Kristian Kiili. 2005. Digital game-based learning: Towards an experiential gaming model. *The Internet and Higher Education* 8, 1 (2005), 13–24. doi:10.1016/j.iheduc.2004.12.001
- [9] Jeanine Krath, Linda Schurmann, and Harald F.O. von Korfflesch. 2021. Revealing the theoretical basis of gamification: A systematic review and analysis of theory in research on gamification, serious games and game-based learning. *Computers in Human Behavior* 125 (2021), 106963. doi:10.1016/j.chb.2021.106963
- [10] Petros Lamerias, Sylvester Arnab, Ian Dunwell, Craig Stewart, Samantha Clarke, and Panagiotis Petridis. 2016. Essential features of serious games design in higher education: Linking learning attributes to game mechanics: Essential features of serious games design. *British Journal of Educational Technology* 48 (05 2016). doi:10.1111/bjet.12467
- [11] Georgios Lampropoulos, Euclid Keramopoulos, Konstantinos Diamantaras, and Georgios Evangelidis. 2023. Integrating Augmented Reality, Gamification, and Serious Games in Computer Science Education. *Education Sciences* 13, 6 (2023). doi:10.3390/educsci13060618
- [12] Dario Liberona, Juan Soto-Correa, Gabriela Rojas-Trempe, and Fernando G. Gutierrez. 2021. Serious Games Usage in Higher Education: Experiences and Guidelines. In *Serious Games. Communications in Computer and Information Science*, Vol. 1428. Springer, Cham, 137–149. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-81351-2_12
- [13] Joseph Loscalzo and Albert-Laszlo Barabasi. 2011. Systems biology and the future of medicine. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Systems Biology and Medicine* 3, 6 (2011), 619–627.
- [14] Ernst Mayr. 2004. *What makes biology unique?: considerations on the autonomy of a scientific discipline*. Cambridge University Press.
- [15] Jaziar Radiani, Tim A. Majchrzak, Jennifer Fromm, and Isabell Wohlgenannt. 2020. A systematic review of immersive virtual reality applications for higher education: Design elements, lessons learned, and research agenda. *Computers & Education* 147 (2020), 103778. doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103778
- [16] Adam M. Ross, Matthew E. Fitzgerald, and Donna H. Rhodes. 2014. Game-based Learning for Systems Engineering Concepts. *Procedia Computer Science* 28 (2014), 430–440. doi:10.1016/j.procs.2014.03.053 2014 Conference on Systems Engineering Research.
- [17] Soumia Yamoul, Lynda Ouchouka, Mohamed Moussetad, and Mohamed Radid. 2023. Systematic Review of Serious Games in Higher Education: Objectives, Benefits, Limitations, and Perspectives. In *2023 7th IEEE Congress on Information Science and Technology (CIST)*. 450–453. doi:10.1109/CIST56084.2023.10409880
- [18] Amal Abdullah Alhebshi and Nada Gamlo. 2022. The Effects of Mobile Game-Based Learning on Saudi EFL Foundation Year Students' Vocabulary Acquisition. *Arab World English Journal* 13, 1 (March 2022), 408–425. doi:10.24093/awej/vol13no1.27
- [19] Kadriye Funda Akaltan, Canan Onder, aıl Vural, Kaan Orhan, Nihan Akdoğan, and Cemal Atakan. 2023. The effect of game-based learning on basic life support skills training for undergraduate dental students. *Journal of Dental Education* 87, 10 (Oct. 2023), 1458–1468. doi:10.1002/jdd.13303
- [20] Zina Alaswad. 2022. Instructional Design and Evaluation of a Game-Based Learning Interior Design Studio. *The International Journal of Design Education* 16, 2 (2022), 113–129. doi:10.18848/2325-128X/CGP/v16i02/113-129
- [21] Berenice Alfaro-Ponce, Azeneth Patino, and Jorge Sanabria-Z. 2023. Components of computational thinking in citizen science games and its contribution to reasoning for complexity through digital game-based learning: A framework proposal. *Cogent Education* 10, 1 (Dec. 2023), 2191751. doi:10.1080/2331186X.2023.2191751
- [22] Fernando Almeida and Zoltan Buzady. 2023. Exploring the Impact of a Serious Game in the Academic Success of Entrepreneurship Students. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems* 51, 4 (June 2023), 436–454. doi:10.1177/00472395231153187
- [23] Shirly Avargil. 2022. Knowledge and Skills of University Students in Chemistry-Related Departments as Expressed in a Specially Designed Escape-Room. *Journal of Science Education and Technology* 31, 5 (Oct. 2022), 680–690. doi:10.1007/s10956-022-09986-9
- [24] Chitra Balakrishna. 2023. The Impact of In-Classroom Non-Digital Game-Based Learning Activities on Students Transitioning to Higher Education. *Education Sciences* 13, 4 (March 2023), 328. doi:10.3390/educsci13040328
- [25] Thomas Bjorn, Sofie Daniel Andersen, Emilie Sommer, Kristine Fogh Andersen, Marius Frederik Qvarnstrom, Mie Moller Enevoldsen, Nicolai Lennart Larsson, and Stacia Suwan Sorensen. 2024. A Serious Game for Promoting Knowledge about Suicidal Thoughts for Students at Higher Education. In *Proceedings of the 2024 International Conference on Information Technology for Social Good*. ACM, Bremen Germany, 342–349. doi:10.1145/3677525.3678680
- [26] Paola Cabrera-Solano. 2022. Game-Based Learning in Higher Education: The Pedagogical Effect of Genially Games in English as a Foreign Language Instruction. *International Journal of Educational Methodology* 8, 4 (Nov. 2022), 719–729. doi:10.12973/ijem.8.4.719
- [27] Murat Perit Cakir, Nur Akkuş akir, Hasan Ayaz, and Frank J. Lee. 2015. An Optical Brain Imaging Study on the Improvements in Mathematical Fluency from Game-based Learning. In *Proceedings of the 2015 Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play*. ACM, London United Kingdom, 209–219. doi:10.1145/2793107.2793133
- [28] Elena Carrion Candel and Louisa Mortimore. 2025. BREAKOUT: SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN TEACHER TRAINING THROUGH ESPAPE ROOMS. *Profesorado, Revista de Curriculum y Formacion del Profesorado* 29, 1 (March 2025), 77–101. doi:10.30827/profesorado.v29i1.30722
- [29] Adam Case. 2022. Using Computer Game Software in a First-Year Seminar and its Effects on Students' Creative Self-Efficacy, Creative Personal Identity, and Insight Problem Solving Abilities. *TechTrends* 66, 4 (July 2022), 631–642. doi:10.1007/s11528-022-00736-7
- [30] Chung-Shing Chan, Yat-hang Chan, and Tsz Heung Agnes Fong. 2020. Game-based e-learning for urban tourism education through an online scenario game. *International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education* 29, 4 (Oct. 2020), 283–300. doi:10.1080/10382046.2019.1698834
- [31] Sumie Chan and Noble Lo. 2021. Impacts of Gamification in Remote Learning in Tertiary Education. In *Proceedings of the 2021 7th International Conference on e-Society, e-Learning and e-Technologies*. ACM, Portsmouth United Kingdom, 26–34. doi:10.1145/3477282.3477290
- [32] Chi-Cheng Chang and Szu-Ting Yang. 2023. Interactive effects of scaffolding digital game-based learning and cognitive style on adult learners' emotion, cognitive load and learning performance. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education* 20, 1 (March 2023), 16. doi:10.1186/s41239-023-00385-7
- [33] Ching-Yi Chang, Hsiu-Ju Jen, and Jie Chi Yang. 2024. Integrating scenario game-based learning with the experiential learning strategy to facilitate nursing students' learning performance and core competencies in labor support training. *Interactive Learning Environments* 32, 10 (Nov. 2024), 7170–7185. doi:10.1080/10494820.2024.2308092
- [34] Xingrong Chen, Di Zhang, Hongfeng Zhang, Kaiyue Shu, Xiaoyu Wei, and Fanbo Li. 2023. The Influence of Quizizz-online Gamification on Vocabulary Learning Effectiveness and Engagement among College EFL Learners in China. In *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Education and Training Technologies*. ACM, Macau China, 1–8. doi:10.1145/3599640.3599651
- [35] Chidera Chinedu Ugo. 2024. Mobile Escape Rooms for Learning Programming in Nigerian Higher Institutions. In *Proceedings of the 24th Koli Calling International Conference on Computing Education Research*. ACM, Koli Finland, 1–3. doi:10.1145/3699538.3699570
- [36] Shih-Ting Chu, Gwo-Jen Hwang, Shu-Yun Chien, and Shao-Chen Chang. 2023. Incorporating teacher intelligence into digital games: An expert system-guided self-regulated learning approach to promoting EFL students' performance in digital gaming contexts. *British Journal of Educational Technology* 54, 2 (March 2023), 534–553. doi:10.1111/bjet.13260
- [37] Laura Creighton, Gary Mitchell, Conor Hamilton, Stephanie Craig, Patrick Stark, Nuala McLaughlin-Borlace, Christine Slade, and Christine Brown Wilson. 2025. Integrating academic and professional integrity: a co-designed serious game for nursing students - a multi-methods study. *International Journal for Educational Integrity* 21, 1 (Feb. 2025), 8. doi:10.1007/s40979-025-00181-y
- [38] Jaione Cubero-Ibanez, Maria Soledad Ibarra-Saiz, and Gregorio Rodriguez-Gomez. 2017. Assessment literacy through serious games in virtual learning environments. In *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality*. ACM, Cadiz Spain, 1–5.

Papers Included in Review

- doi:10.1145/3144826.3145375
- [39] Mariam Dabbous, Anwar Kawtharani, Iqbal Fahs, Zahraa Hallal, Dina Shouman, Marwan Akel, Mohamad Rahal, and Fouad Sakr. 2022. The Role of Game-Based Learning in Experiential Education: Tool Validation, Motivation Assessment, and Outcomes Evaluation among a Sample of Pharmacy Students. *Education Sciences* 12, 7 (June 2022), 434. doi:10.3390/educsci12070434
- [40] Chih-Pu Dai, Fengfeng Ke, and Yanjun Pan. 2022. Narrative-supported math problem solving in digital game-based learning. *Educational technology research and development* 70, 4 (Aug. 2022), 1261–1281. doi:10.1007/s11423-022-10129-5
- [41] Edith Debrenti. 2024. Using Digital Game-Based Learning in Mathematics Education: A Case Study with Teacher Training Students. *International Journal for Technology in Mathematics Education* 31, 3 (Sept. 2024), 153–162. doi:10.1564/tme_v31.3.06
- [42] Thaleia Denizou, Mariza Dima, and Chris Cox. 2020. Designing a Game to Help Higher Education Students Develop Their Note-Taking Skills. In *Proceedings of the Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play*. ACM, Virtual Event Canada, 181–192. doi:10.1145/3410404.3414230
- [43] Eleni Dermentzi. 2024. Using game-based learning and online flipped classrooms with degree apprenticeship students. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 40, 2 (April 2024), 494–509. doi:10.1111/jcal.12896
- [44] Ai-Chu Elisha Ding, Jessica DuBois, Sunaina Asher, Michael Mick, and Huali Fu. 2025. Let's make a game! A case of co-designing with teachers from a research-practice partnership to integrate a virtual reality-enhanced digital game-based learning science unit. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education* 57, 4 (July 2025), 784–799. doi:10.1080/15391523.2024.2313619
- [45] Yara Elenany and Vian Ahmed. 2024. A Digital Simulation Game for Resource Management in Construction Projects. *Electronic Journal of e-Learning* 22, 10 (Dec. 2024), 01–18. doi:10.34190/ejel.22.10.3495
- [46] Sandra Elsom, Colleen Stieler-Hunt, and Margaret Marshman. 2023. Supporting learning in higher education with a curriculum-embedded alternate reality game. *Interactive Learning Environments* (Jan. 2023), 1–12. doi:10.1080/10494820.2023.2167838
- [47] Andrew Emerson, Wookhee Min, Roger Azevedo, and James Lester. 2023. Early prediction of student knowledge in game-based learning with distributed representations of assessment questions. *British Journal of Educational Technology* 54, 1 (Jan. 2023), 40–57. doi:10.1111/bjet.13281
- [48] Andrew Emerson, Robert Sawyer, Roger Azevedo, and James Lester. 2018. Gaze-Enhanced Student Modeling for Game-based Learning. In *Proceedings of the 26th Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization*. ACM, Singapore Singapore, 63–72. doi:10.1145/3209219.3209238
- [49] Rosa Estriegana, Jose Medina, Rafael Robina, and Roberto Barchino. 2021. Virtual Learning Environment to Encourage Students' Relationships and Cooperative Competence Acquisition. In *Proceedings of the 26th ACM Conference on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education V. 1*. ACM, Virtual Event Germany, 53–59. doi:10.1145/3430665.3456363
- [50] A Fredrick Ruban, P Banumathi, Mathusha Sam Lara, and others. 2021. EXAMINING THE INTEREST AND ADAPTABILITY OF UNDERGRADUATE RURAL STUDENTS TO GAMIFICATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. *Ilkogretim Online* 20, 5 (2021).
- [51] Aleksandra Gawel, Sergiusz Strykowski, and Konstantinos Madias. 2022. Implementing Sustainability into Virtual Simulation Games in Business Higher Education. *Education Sciences* 12, 9 (Sept. 2022), 599. doi:10.3390/educsci12090599
- [52] Greg Gay. 2021. Teaching accessibility awareness with games. In *Proceedings of the 18th International Web for All Conference*. ACM, Ljubljana Slovenia, 1–3. doi:10.1145/3430263.3452438
- [53] Centeno George, Egusquiza Carlos, and Mauricio David. 2017. Serious Game for the Virtual Practice of the Emplastillado in the Constructive System of adobe with reinforced cane. In *Proceedings of the 2017 9th International Conference on Education Technology and Computers*. ACM, Barcelona Spain, 99–103. doi:10.1145/3175536.3175554
- [54] Iwona Grobelna, Malgorzata Mazurkiewicz, and Damian Janus. 2022. Help students learn interpreted Petri nets with Minecraft. *Informatics in Education* (July 2022). doi:10.15388/infedu.2023.13
- [55] Kevin Hartman, Shun Geng Ng, Aishwarya Lakshminarasimhan, Thangamani Ramasamy, Melika Farahani, and Chris Boesch. 2019. Achievements for building a learning community. In *Proceedings of the Sixth (2019) ACM Conference on Learning @ Scale*. ACM, Chicago IL USA, 1–4. doi:10.1145/3330430.3333672
- [56] Hadi Hosseini, Maxwell Hartt, and Mehrnaz Mostafapour. 2019. Learning IS Child's Play: Game-Based Learning in Computer Science Education. *ACM Transactions on Computing Education* 19, 3 (Sept. 2019), 1–18. doi:10.1145/3282844
- [57] Xiao Hu. 2025. Navigating the sojourn: a mixed-methods exploration of game-based approaches for enhancing intercultural adaptation among Chinese international higher education students in Australia. *Discover Education* 4, 1 (Jan. 2025), 5. doi:10.1007/s44217-025-00399-5
- [58] Zijing Hu. 2024. Game-Based Learning: Alternative Approaches to Teaching and Learning Strategies in Health Sciences Education. *Educational Process International Journal* 13, 2 (2024). doi:10.22521/edupij.2024.132.6
- [59] Zijing Hu and Radmila Razlog. 2023. The use of game-based learning to enhance student engagement in the acupuncture programme: South African students' opinions. *Journal for the Education of Gifted Young Scientists* 11, 2 (July 2023), 137–152. doi:10.17478/jegys.1277401
- [60] Hsiu-Ting Hung, Jie Chi Yang, and Ching-Jung Chung. 2025. Effects of Performance Goal Orientations on English Translation Techniques in Digital Game-Based Learning. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* 41, 9 (May 2025), 5575–5590. doi:10.1080/10447318.2024.2364474
- [61] Alessio Iannetti. 2025. Who wants to be a millionaire? A game-based approach to enhancing engagement and teamwork in immunology education. *Frontiers in Education* 10 (July 2025), 1601835. doi:10.3389/educ.2025.1601835
- [62] International Student Advisors of Japan (ISA), Tokyo, Japan, semuelolayvar@gmail.com and Samuel R. Olayvar. 2023. Integration of Game-Based Learning Approach as an Innovative Teaching Tool in Improving Students' Academic Performance in English. *International Journal of Instruction* 16, 3 (July 2023), 677–690. doi:10.29333/iji.2023.16336a
- [63] Elina Jääskä, Jaakko Kujala, and Kirsi Aaltonen. 2023. A game-based learning method to teach project management – the case of the earned value management. *Cogent Education* 10, 2 (Dec. 2023), 2264035. doi:10.1080/2331186X.2023.2264035
- [64] Ilish Kane, Chuy-Thuy Pham, Adam Wade Lewis, and Vanessa Miller. 2019. Escape from the Python's Den: An Educational Game for Teaching Programming to Younger Students. In *Proceedings of the 2019 ACM Southeast Conference*. ACM, Kennesaw GA USA, 279–280. doi:10.1145/3299815.3314477
- [65] Nuri Kara. 2024. A Mixed-Methods Study of Cultural Heritage Learning through Playing a Serious Game. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* 40, 6 (March 2024), 1397–1408. doi:10.1080/10447318.2022.2125627
- [66] Juka S. Kim, Karen L. Leung, Isabel K. Eng, and Aparna Sridhar. 2024. Surgical education for medical students: Virtual game-based learning. *Medical Education* 58, 5 (May 2024), 588–589. doi:10.1111/medu.15332
- [67] Jae-woo Kim and Robert Hanneman. 2023. Teaching Social Dilemma through Simulating Cooperation: A Classroom Experiment. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice* 20, 6 (Aug. 2023). doi:10.53761/1.20.6.3
- [68] Devorah Kletenik and Deborah Sturm. 2018. Game Development with a Serious Focus. In *Proceedings of the 49th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education*. ACM, Baltimore Maryland USA, 652–657. doi:10.1145/3159450.3159588
- [69] Marco Klopp, Antonia Dörringer, Tobias Eigler, Paula Bartel, Marvin Hochstetter, Andreas Weishaupt, Philipp Geirhos, Jörg Abke, Georg Hagel, Jens Elsebach, and Raphael Rossmann. 2023. Development of an Authoring Tool for the Creation of Individual 3D Game-Based Learning Environments. In *Proceedings of the 5th European Conference on Software Engineering Education*. ACM, Seoon/Bavaria Germany, 204–209. doi:10.1145/3593663.3593689
- [70] Georgios Lampropoulos, Euclid Keramopoulos, Konstantinos Diamantaras, and Georgios Evangelidis. 2023. Integrating Augmented Reality, Gamification, and Serious Games in Computer Science Education. *Education Sciences* 13, 6 (June 2023), 618. doi:10.3390/educsci13060618
- [71] Jared Ordoña Lim, Grace Barkhuff, Jane Awuah, Sophie Clyde, Riya Sogani, Christina Gardner-McCune, David Touretzky, and Judith Odili Uchidiuno. 2025. Escape or D13: Understanding Youth Perspectives of AI through Educational Game Co-design. In *Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, Yokohama Japan, 1–17. doi:10.1145/3706598.3714037
- [72] Wan Quan Lin. 2024. Serious Game Design and Evaluation Through Prototyping: A Case Study of Developing a Virtual Reality Serious Game for Vocational Education and Training. In *Proceeding of the 2024 8th International Conference on Education and E-Learning*. ACM, Tokyo Japan, 98–104. doi:10.1145/3719487.3719498
- [73] Yu-Cheng Lin and Huei-Tse Hou. 2024. Designing a Strategic Analysis and Planning Skills Training Board Game Using Mobile Technology and a Dual-Scaffolding Mechanism. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher* 33, 2 (April 2024), 431–445. doi:10.1007/s40299-023-00740-2
- [74] Dai Linyi. 2022. Analysis of the Teaching Design Process Mode of College English Application Oriented Curriculum with NLP Voice Data Authentication. *ACM Transactions on Asian and Low-Resource Language Information Processing* (July 2022), 3529392. doi:10.1145/3529392
- [75] Trisha Litz and Kevin Pyatt. 2017. Using an educational game to increase student engagement & learning. *Journal of Computing Sciences in Colleges* 33, 2 (2017), 129–133.
- [76] Trisha Litz and Kevin Pyatt. 2017. Using an educational game to increase student engagement & learning. *Journal of Computing Sciences in Colleges* 33, 2 (2017), 129–133. Publisher: Consortium for Computing Sciences in Colleges.
- [77] Lo-An Liu and Gwo-Jen Hwang. 2024. Effects of metalinguistic corrective feedback on novice EFL students' digital game-based grammar learning performances, perceptions and behavioural patterns. *British Journal of Educational Technology* 55, 2 (March 2024), 687–711. doi:10.1111/bjet.13400
- [78] Aida López-Serrano, Nadia McGowan, Pablo Moreno-Ger, and Daniel Burgos. 2025. Teaching soft skills in higher education through serious games: validation of the Compete! gamification. *Smart Learning Environments* 12, 1 (Aug. 2025),

49. doi:10.1186/s40561-025-00401-5
- [79] Abdulrahman M. Alshabeh. 2024. Learning Vocabulary via Video Games: A Case Study of Saudi University Students. *Arab World English Journal* 15, 3 (Sept. 2024), 321–332. doi:10.24093/awej/vol15no3.19
- [80] Eleni G. Makri. 2022. Does the Cards against Calamity Learning Game Facilitate Attitudes toward Negotiation, Civics, and Sustainability? Empirical Findings from Greek Graduates. *Education Sciences* 12, 11 (Oct. 2022), 738. doi:10.3390/educsci12110738
- [81] Dina Altayevna Malgazhdarova, Gulzira Kabayevna Kenzhetayeva, and Ismail Hakki Mirici. 2024. Application of Communicative Game-based Learning Project "Aengine" for Teaching Grammar EFL Classrooms. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)* (Oct. 2024). doi:10.5281/ZENODO.13338632 Publisher: Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language).
- [82] Agostino Marengo, Alessandro Pagano, and Kamal Ahmed Soomro. 2024. Serious games to assess university students' soft skills: investigating the effectiveness of a gamified assessment prototype. *Interactive Learning Environments* 32, 10 (Nov. 2024), 6142–6158. doi:10.1080/10494820.2023.2253849
- [83] Michael Melville, Chad Hershock, and B Reeya-Jayan. 2024. Virtual Engineering in Minecraft: Helping Students Visualize and Manipulate the Properties of Materials. *Advances in Engineering Education* 12, 2 (2024). doi:10.18260/3-1-1153-36059
- [84] Kamal Omari, Mohamed Moussetad, El Houssine Labriji, and Said Harchi. 2020. Proposal for a New Tool to Evaluate a Serious Game. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)* 15, 17 (Sept. 2020), 238. doi:10.3991/ijet.v15i17.15253
- [85] Yanjun Pan, Fengfeng Ke, and Chih-Pu Dai. 2023. Patterns of Using Multimodal External Representations in Digital Game-Based Learning. *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 60, 8 (Jan. 2023), 1918–1941. doi:10.1177/07356331221087771
- [86] Luka Petrović, Danijela Stojanović, Svetlana Mitrović, Dušan Barać, and Zorica Bogdanović. 2021. Designing an extended smart classroom: An approach to game-based learning for IoT. *Computer Applications in Engineering Education* (July 2021), cae.22446. doi:10.1002/cae.22446
- [87] Dorina Pojani and Roberto Rocco. 2023. Edutainment: Role-Playing versus Serious Gaming in Planning Education. *Journal of Planning Education and Research* 43, 3 (Sept. 2023), 585–597. doi:10.1177/0739456X20902251
- [88] Nicholas Polys, Jessica Hotter, Madison Lanier, Laura Purcell, Jordan Wolf, W. Cully Hession, Peter Sforza, and James D. Ivory. 2017. Finding frogs: using game-based learning to increase environmental awareness. In *Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on 3D Web Technology*. ACM, Brisbane Queensland Australia, 1–8. doi:10.1145/3055624.3075955
- [89] Pitchada Prasittichok, Suradet Jitprapaikularn, Khawanying Sriprasertpap, and Gwo-Jen Hwang. 2024. Technological solutions to fostering students' moral courage: an augmented reality-based contextual gaming approach. *Cogent Education* 11, 1 (Dec. 2024), 2378276. doi:10.1080/2331186X.2024.2378276
- [90] Damar Isti Pratiwi and Budi Waluyo. 2022. INTEGRATING TASK- AND GAME-BASED LEARNING INTO AN ONLINE TOEFL PREPARATION COURSE DURING COVID-19 OUTBREAK. *Malaysian Journal of Learning and Instruction* 19 (2022). doi:10.32890/mjli2022.19.2.2
- [91] Monika Rajcsanyi-Molnar, Istvan Andras, and Sandor Czifra. 2025. Integrating Serious Games and Gamification for Diverse Learner Groups: Lessons from the "GeoGecko" Project. *Education Sciences* 15, 4 (March 2025), 440. doi:10.3390/educsci15040440
- [92] Wendy M. Robertson. 2022. Increasing student engagement and comprehension of the global water cycle through game-based learning in undergraduate courses. *Journal of Geoscience Education* 70, 2 (April 2022), 161–175. doi:10.1080/10899995.2021.1977030
- [93] Victor Travassos Sarinho. 2019. Masters of the Process: A Board Game Proposal for Teaching Software Management and Software Development Process. In *Proceedings of the XXXIII Brazilian Symposium on Software Engineering*. ACM, Salvador Brazil, 532–536. doi:10.1145/3350768.3352459
- [94] Kyle W. Scholz, Jolanta N. Komornicka, and Andrew Moore. 2021. Gamifying History: Designing and Implementing a Game-Based Learning Course Design Framework. *Teaching & Learning Inquiry* 9, 1 (March 2021), 99–116. doi:10.20343/teachlearninq.9.1.9
- [95] School of Foreigner Language, Baise University, China, 89520829@qq.com, Lin Li, Mayuree Suacamram, Graduate School, Western University, Thailand & School of Foreigner Language, Baise University, China, m.suacamram@gmail.com, Napaporn Tanya, and Graduate School, Western University, Thailand, tanyanaporn9577@gmail.com. 2023. Game Design to Improve Thai Speaking Skills for Chinese Students. *International Journal of Instruction* 16, 1 (Jan. 2023), 741–752. doi:10.29333/iji.2023.16141a
- [96] Rui Silva, Ricardo Rodrigues, and Carmem Leal. 2021. Games based learning in accounting education – which dimensions are the most relevant? *Accounting Education* 30, 2 (March 2021), 159–187. doi:10.1080/09639284.2021.1891107
- [97] Kawin Sipiyanuk, Stylianos Hatzipanagos, Tippanart Vichayanrat, Patricia A. Reynolds, and Jennifer E. Gallagher. 2022. Evaluating a Dental Public-Health Game across Two Learning Contexts. *Education Sciences* 12, 8 (July 2022), 517. doi:10.3390/educsci12080517
- [98] Kirsi Syyinimaa, Kirsi Lainema, and Timo Lainema. 2024. Higher Education Students' Experiences of Game-Based Learning - Fostering and Hampering Aspects in Virtual Teamwork. *International Journal of Technology in Education* 7, 4 (Nov. 2024), 754–780. doi:10.46328/ijte.860
- [99] Szilvia Szilágyi, Enikő Palencsár, Attila Körei, and Zsuzsanna Török. 2025. Examining the Effectiveness of Non-Digital Game-Based Learning Among University Computer Science Students on the Topic of Improper Integrals. *Education Sciences* 15, 2 (Jan. 2025), 132. doi:10.3390/educsci15020132
- [100] Szilvia Szilágyi, Anna Mária Takács, Attila Körei, and Zsuzsanna Török. 2025. Using Game-Based Learning for Engaging with Determinants in Mathematics Education at the University Level. *Education Sciences* 15, 10 (Oct. 2025), 1329. doi:10.3390/educsci15101329
- [101] Yuan-Yu Teng, Wen-Chi Chou, and Meng-Tzu Cheng. 2021. Learning immunology in a game: Learning outcomes, the use of player characters, immersion experiences and visual attention distributions. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 37, 2 (April 2021), 475–486. doi:10.1111/jcal.12501
- [102] Chun-Yen Tsai, Yun-An Chen, Fu-Pei Hsieh, Min-Hsiung Chuang, and Chien-Liang Lin. 2024. Effects of a Programming Course Using the GAME Model on Undergraduates' Self-Efficacy and Basic Programming Concepts. *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 62, 3 (June 2024), 482–504. doi:10.1177/07356331231206071
- [103] Atik Umamah. 2022. Digital Game-Based Learning (DGBL): The Voice of EFL University Students and Teachers. *PASAA* 63, 1 (Jan. 2022), 279–314. doi:10.58837/CHULA.PASAA.63.1.11
- [104] Poomsri Vate-U-Lan and Desmond Cahill. 2024. Advancing academic achievement: integrating society 5.0 and game-based learning in metaverse space for undergraduates in Bangkok, Thailand. *Cogent Education* 11, 1 (Dec. 2024), 2385239. doi:10.1080/2331186X.2024.2385239
- [105] Kelvin Wan, Vivian King, and Kevin Chan. 2021. Examining Essential Flow Antecedents to promote students' Self-Regulated Learning and Acceptance of Use in a Game-Based Learning classroom. *Electronic Journal of e-Learning* 19, 6 (Nov. 2021), pp531–547. doi:10.34190/ejel.19.6.2117
- [106] Chun-Ping Wu, Jie Tu, and Shu-ling Wu. 2018. Design a reflective mechanism to engage students in student-constructed test activity. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Information and Education Technology*. ACM, Osaka Japan, 106–110. doi:10.1145/3178158.3178178
- [107] Xiao-Ming Wang, Wen-Qing Zhou, Gwo-Jen Hwang, Shi-Man Wang, and Xiao-Tong Huang. 2024. The mediating and moderating role of cognitive engagement in the relationship between prior knowledge and learning achievement in game-based learning. *Educational Technology & Society* 27, 4 (Oct. 2024). doi:10.30191/ETS.202410_27(4).RP08
- [108] Takahiko Yamamor, Takahiro Hayashi, Mayumi Kato, and Mika Toff. 2025. A New Approach to Medical English for Physiotherapy and Occupational Therapy Students: Integrating Phonics, Grammar, and Clinical Communication. *Journal of Medical English Education* 24, 2 (June 2025).
- [109] Jie Chi Yang, Ching-Jung Chung, and Mei-Shan Chen. 2022. Effects of performance goal orientations on learning performance and in-game performance in digital game-based learning. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 38, 2 (April 2022), 422–439. doi:10.1111/jcal.12622
- [110] Li Ye, Jingyi Li, Simin Yang, and Yongxin Hang. 2024. The effect of augmented reality-based serious game on traditional pattern learning. *Interactive Learning Environments* 32, 10 (Nov. 2024), 7559–7587. doi:10.1080/10494820.2024.2327042
- [111] Yuan Ze University, Taiwan, gsyulin@gmail.com and Yulin Chen. 2023. Integrating a Game-Based App to Enhance Translation Learners' Engagement, Motivation, and Performance. *International Journal of Instruction* 16, 2 (April 2023), 759–782. doi:10.29333/iji.2023.16240a
- [112] Sergio A. Zabala-Vargas, Lewis H. Garcia-Mora, Edgar Arciniegas-Hernandez, Jerson I Reina-Medrano, Bárbara De Benito-Crosetti, and Antonia Darder-Mésquida. 2021. Strengthening Motivation in the Mathematical Engineering Teaching Processes – A Proposal from Gamification and Game-Based Learning. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)* 16, 06 (March 2021), 4. doi:10.3991/ijet.v16i06.16163
- [113] Nicoletta Zerman, Roberta Silva, Elisa Bonfadelli, Susanna Puecher, Gianna Marogna, Rachele De'Manzoni, Marinella Beccherle, and Luigina Mortari. 2025. Game-Based Learning to Promote Clinical Reasoning: An Innovative Educational Proposal in Pediatric Dentistry. *Education Sciences* 15, 2 (Feb. 2025), 190. doi:10.3390/educsci15020190
- [114] Yuchun Zhong, Luke Kutzik Fryer, Shiyue Zheng, Alex Shum, and Samuel Kai Wah Chu. 2025. From gaming to reality: effectiveness of skills transfer from competitive sandbox gaming environment to near and far contexts. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education* 22, 1 (Jan. 2025), 1. doi:10.1186/s41239-024-00500-2
- [115] Di Zou, Ruofei Zhang, Haoran Xie, and Fu Lee Wang. 2021. Digital game-based learning of information literacy: Effects of gameplay modes on university students' learning performance, motivation, self-efficacy and flow experiences. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology* 37, 2 (May 2021), 152–170. doi:10.

14742/ajet.6682

Papers Excluded - Literature Reviews

- [116] Surattana Adipat, Kittisak Laksana, Kanrawee Busayanon, Alongkorn Ausawasowan, and Boonlit Adipat. 2021. Engaging Students in the Learning Process with Game-Based Learning: The Fundamental Concepts. *International Journal of Technology in Education* 4, 3 (July 2021), 542–552. doi:10.46328/ijte.169
- [117] Omar Amzari, Maizatul Hayati Mohamad Yatim, Erni Marlina Saari, and Sulaiman Anter. 2025. Thematic Analysis of Student's Reflections on ProNaja X2 – Board Game in Learning Basic Programming. *Journal of ICT in Education* 12, 1 (April 2025), 65–74. doi:10.37134/jictie.vol12.1.5.2025
- [118] Rizky Fauzy Ananda, Rita Milyartini, and Yudi Sukmayadi. 2025. Mapping the Use of Digital Game-Based Learning in Music Education: A Scoping Review. *Jurnal Pendidikan Indonesia* 6, 11 (2025), 4982–4989.
- [119] Seyyed Kazem Banihashem, Hojjat Dehghanzadeh, Douglas Clark, Omid Noroozi, and Harm J. A. Biemans. 2024. Learning analytics for online game-based learning: a systematic literature review. *Behaviour & Information Technology* 43, 12 (Sept. 2024), 2689–2716. doi:10.1080/0144929X.2023.2255301
- [120] Lea C. Brandl and Andreas Schrader. 2024. Serious Games in Higher Education in the Transforming Process to Education 4.0—Systematized Review. *Education Sciences* 14, 3 (March 2024), 281. doi:10.3390/educsci14030281
- [121] Manuel Bächtold, Jacqueline Papet, Dominique Barbe Asensio, and Apollinaire Ngoua Ondo. 2024. Direct instruction or active learning? The spectrum of first-year university teaching practices. *Higher Education Research & Development* 43, 8 (Nov. 2024), 1704–1720. doi:10.1080/07294360.2024.2366318
- [122] Zhihui Cai, Peipei Mao, Dandan Wang, Jinbo He, Xinjie Chen, and Xitao Fan. 2022. Effects of Scaffolding in Digital Game-Based Learning on Student's Achievement: a Three-Level Meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review* 34, 2 (June 2022), 537–574. doi:10.1007/s10648-021-09655-0
- [123] Angela Carman, Christy Brady, and Trey Conatser. 2022. Game Design for High-Order Thinking in Review Activities. *College Teaching* 70, 1 (Jan. 2022), 119–123. doi:10.1080/87567555.2020.1865254
- [124] Derek L. Choi-Lundberg, Kerryn Butler-Henderson, Kristyn Harman, and Joseph Crawford. 2023. A systematic review of digital innovations in technology-enhanced learning designs in higher education. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology* (Oct. 2023), 133–162. doi:10.14742/ajet.7615
- [125] Marcel Fernandes Dallaqua, Breno Nunes, and Marly M. Carvalho. 2024. Serious games research streams for social change: Critical review and framing. *British Journal of Educational Technology* 55, 2 (March 2024), 460–483. doi:10.1111/bjjet.13404
- [126] Cansu Cigdem Ekin and Abdulmenaf Gul. 2022. Bibliometric Analysis of Game-Based Researches in Educational Research. *International Journal of Technology in Education* 5, 3 (Aug. 2022), 499–517. doi:10.46328/ijte.341
- [127] Büşra Ergin. 2024. Game Method in Education in Web-Based Information Resources: Readability Analysis. (Oct. 2024). doi:10.5281/ZENODO.13894317 Publisher: Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language).
- [128] Odile Estrada Molina, Dieter Reynaldo Fuentes-Cancell, and Alien García-Hernández. 2022. Evaluating usability in educational technology: A systematic review from the teaching of mathematics. *LUMAT: International Journal on Math, Science and Technology Education* 10, 1 (Feb. 2022). doi:10.31129/LUMAT.10.1.1686
- [129] Fernando Fernández-Gómez, Maria Cosin-Villanueva, Pedro Almiñana-Pastor, and Andrés López-Roldán. 2025. A comparative analysis of game-based learning and conventional learning in dental education. *Journal of Dental Education* 89, 3 (March 2025), 414–420. doi:10.1002/jdd.13747
- [130] Ivar Svare Holand, Peter Mozelius, and Trond Olav Skevik. 2022. Implementation of Emergency Management Exercises as Alternate Reality Games – Students' Perceptions. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)* 17, 06 (March 2022), 181–193. doi:10.3991/ijet.v17i06.27937
- [131] Amina Khaldi, Rokia Bouzidi, and Fahima Nader. 2023. Gamification of e-learning in higher education: a systematic literature review. *Smart Learning Environments* 10, 1 (Jan. 2023), 10. doi:10.1186/s40561-023-00227-z
- [132] Min Lan and Xiaofeng Zhou. 2025. A qualitative systematic review on AI empowered self-regulated learning in higher education. *npj Science of Learning* 10, 1 (May 2025), 21. doi:10.1038/s41539-025-00319-0
- [133] Hao Lei, Ming Ming Chiu, Danyi Wang, Chenxin Wang, and Tongwei Xie. 2022. Effects of Game-Based Learning on Students' Achievement in Science: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 60, 6 (Oct. 2022), 1373–1398. doi:10.1177/07356331211064543
- [134] Hao Lei, Chenxin Wang, Ming Ming Chiu, and Shuangye Chen. 2022. Do educational games affect students' achievement emotions? Evidence from a meta-analysis. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 38, 4 (Aug. 2022), 946–959. doi:10.1111/jcal.12664
- [135] Lucie Lendelova, Patrik Hrkút, Michal Duračik, Eliška Čičmancová, and Adriana Panáčková. 2024. Use of management games within the education process of future managers at universities in Slovakia and Czech Republic. *Entrepreneurship*

- and Sustainability Issues 12, 1 (Sept. 2024), 124–137. doi:10.9770/jesi.2024.12.1(9)
- [136] Danielle Lester, Gregory J. Skulmoski, Darren P. Fisher, Vishal Mehrotra, Iris Lim, Alexander Lang, and Justin W. L. Keogh. 2023. Drivers and barriers to the utilisation of gamification and game-based learning in universities: A systematic review of educators' perspectives. *British Journal of Educational Technology* 54, 6 (Nov. 2023), 1748–1770. doi:10.1111/bjjet.13311
- [137] Léa Martinez, Manuel Gimenes, and Eric Lambert. 2022. Entertainment Video Games for Academic Learning: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 60, 5 (Sept. 2022), 1083–1109. doi:10.1177/07356331211053848
- [138] Jewoong Moon, Sheunghyun Yeo, Seyyed Kazem Banihashem, and Omid Noroozi. 2024. Using multimodal learning analytics as a formative assessment tool: Exploring collaborative dynamics in mathematics teacher education. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 40, 6 (Dec. 2024), 2753–2771. doi:10.1111/jcal.13028
- [139] Azeneth Patiño, María Soledad Ramirez-Montoya, and Mariana Buenestado-Fernández. 2023. Active learning and education 4.0 for complex thinking training: analysis of two case studies in open education. *Smart Learning Environments* 10, 1 (Jan. 2023), 8. doi:10.1186/s40561-023-00229-x
- [140] Xing-yue Qiu, Chuang-Kai Chiu, Lu-Lu Zhao, Cai-Feng Sun, and Shu-jie Chen. 2023. Trends in VR/AR technology-supporting language learning from 2008 to 2019: a research perspective. *Interactive Learning Environments* 31, 4 (May 2023), 2090–2113. doi:10.1080/10494820.2021.1874999
- [141] Melanie A. Robinson, Jean-François Soublière, Marine Agogue, Denis A. Grégoire, Tuvana Rua, and Yves Plourde. 2023. Tackling the anxiety of learning statistics: The mystery of the red envelope. *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education* 21, 3 (July 2023), 167–176. doi:10.1111/dsji.12294
- [142] Risyia Pramana Situmorang, Hadi Suwono, Munzil Munzil, Hendra Susanto, Chun-Yen Chang, and Shan-Yu Liu. 2024. Learn biology using digital game-based learning: A systematic literature review. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education* 20, 6 (June 2024), em2459. doi:10.29333/ejmste/14658
- [143] Maria José Sousa, Fátima Suleman, Pere Mercadé Melé, and Jesús Molina Gómez. 2021. New Research and Trends in Higher Education. *Education Sciences* 11, 9 (Aug. 2021), 456. doi:10.3390/educsci11090456
- [144] Jiahong Su, Kai Guo, Xinyu Chen, and Samuel Kai Wah Chu. 2024. Teaching artificial intelligence in K–12 classrooms: a scoping review. *Interactive Learning Environments* 32, 9 (Oct. 2024), 5207–5226. doi:10.1080/10494820.2023.2212706
- [145] Tan Bee Sian, Tan Wee Hoe, Ahmad Zamzuri Mohammad Ali, and Chong Kim Soon. 2024. EFFECTS OF DIGITAL GAME-BASED LEARNING ON PRODUCT INNOVATION SKILLS DEVELOPMENT: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN APPLIED ARTS AND APPLIED SCIENCE UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS. *Malaysian Journal of Learning and Instruction* 21, 2 (Aug. 2024), 357–386. doi:10.32890/mjli2024.21.2.12
- [146] Feng Tian and Irfan Naufal Umar. 2025. Research Trends of Digital Game-based Learning for Technical Vocabulary Acquisition: A Systematic Decennial Literature Review (2014-2024). *Arab World English Journal* 16, 3 (Sept. 2025), 60–88. doi:10.24093/awej/vol16no3.4
- [147] Chioma Udeozor, Ryo Toyoda, Fernando Russo Abegão, and Jarka Glassey. 2023. Digital games in engineering education: systematic review and future trends. *European Journal of Engineering Education* 48, 2 (March 2023), 321–339. doi:10.1080/03043797.2022.2093168
- [148] Zümürüt Varol Selçuk. 2024. ENHANCING NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSCIENCE EDUCATION THROUGH GAMIFICATION: INVESTIGATI. *International Journal of Education Technology and Scientific Researches* (Jan. 2024), 26. doi:10.35826/ijetsar.732
- [149] Billy T.M. Wong, Kam Cheong Li, and Mengjin Liu. 2025. Smart Education across Academic Disciplines: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange* 18, 1 (2025), 85–108. doi:10.18785/jetde.1801.06
- [150] Erkan Yeşiltaş and Saliha Cevher. 2022. Trends in Research on the Use of Digital Games in Education. *e-International Journal of Educational Research* (June 2022). doi:10.19160/e-ijer.1107500
- [151] Xiao-Li Zheng, Yun-Fang Tu, Gwo-Jen Hwang, Jue Yu, and Yuan-Bo Huang. 2024. Interweaving of self-regulated learning and game-based learning in higher education: a review of academic publications from 2009 to 2020. *Educational technology research and development* 72, 6 (Dec. 2024), 3185–3216. doi:10.1007/s11423-024-10393-7
- [152] Danhua Zhou. 2024. “Learn to Argue” and “Argue to Learn”: meta-analysis of effective instructional design for online scientific argumentation activities. *Interactive Learning Environments* 32, 9 (Oct. 2024), 4857–4880. doi:10.1080/10494820.2023.2205904

Papers Excluded - Not Higher Education

- [153] Anna AlRuheili. 2024. Online Learning Evaluation (Kahoot!) As A Motivational Tool For Students Learning. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice* 30, 8 (2024), 01–06.

- [154] Ishak Nor Asniza, Md Osman Siti Zuraidah, Abdul Rahman Md Baharuddin, Zainal Muhammad Zuhair, and Yakob Nooraida. 2021. Online game-based learning using kahoot! to enhance pre-university students' active learning: A students' perception in biology classroom. *Journal of Turkish Science Education* 18, 1 (March 2021), 145–160. doi:10.36681/tused.2021.57
- [155] Neven Drljević, Ivica Botički, and Lung-Hsiang Wong. 2022. Investigating the different facets of student engagement during augmented reality use in primary school. *British Journal of Educational Technology* 53, 5 (Sept. 2022), 1361–1388. doi:10.1111/bjjet.13197
- [156] Huei-Tse Hou and Su-Han Keng. 2021. A Dual-Scaffolding Framework Integrating Peer-Scaffolding and Cognitive-Scaffolding for an Augmented Reality-Based Educational Board Game: An Analysis of Learners' Collective Flow State and Collaborative Learning Behavioral Patterns. *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 59, 3 (June 2021), 547–573. doi:10.1177/0735633120969409
- [157] Hsiu-Ting Hung and Hui-Chin Yeh. 2023. Augmented-reality-enhanced game-based learning in flipped English-classrooms: Effects on students' creative thinking and vocabulary acquisition. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 39, 6 (Dec. 2023), 1786–1800. doi:10.1111/jcal.12839
- [158] Ungsinun Intarakamhang, Sudarat Tuntivivat, Kanchana Patrawiwat, Pitchada Prasittichok, Nawasap Pichaisamart, Somsamer Thaksin, and Pinyo Wongthong. 2025. Validity of Measurement and Causal Model of Online Scam Protection Behavior Among Risk Thai Students. *European Journal of Educational Research* 14, 2 (April 2025), 661–675. doi:10.12973/eu-jer.14.2.661
- [159] Gerald Knezek, David Gibson, Rhonda Christensen, Ottavia Trevisan, and Morgan Carter. 2023. Assessing approaches to learning with nonparametric multi-dimensional scaling. *British Journal of Educational Technology* 54, 1 (Jan. 2023), 126–141. doi:10.1111/bjjet.13275
- [160] Eyal Liat and Merav Hayak. 2025. The integration of digital games into teaching and learning—A unique constructivist framework. *British Journal of Educational Technology* 56, 5 (Sept. 2025), 2202–2222. doi:10.1111/bjjet.13555
- [161] Yu-Cheng Lin and Huei-Tse Hou. 2024. The evaluation of a scaffolding-based augmented reality educational board game with competition-oriented and collaboration-oriented mechanisms: differences analysis of learning effectiveness, motivation, flow, and anxiety. *Interactive Learning Environments* 32, 2 (Feb. 2024), 502–521. doi:10.1080/10494820.2022.2091606
- [162] Zulkifley Mohamed, Nor Hasbiah Ubaidullah, Noor Wahida Md Junus, Kasthuri Devi Angamuthu, and Ahmad Ahmad. 2024. Modelling computational thinking with game-based learning among primary school students'. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)* 13, 6 (Dec. 2024), 4115. doi:10.11591/ijere.v13i6.28395
- [163] Edina-Timea Opreș, Éva Bálint-Svella, and Iuliana Zsoldos-Marchiș. 2021. Prospective preschool and primary school teachers' knowledge and opinion about gamification. *Acta Didactica Napocensia* 14, 1 (July 2021), 104–114. doi:10.24193/adn.14.1.8
- [164] Manuela Repetto, Barbara Bruschi, and Melania Talarico. 2023. Key issues and pedagogical implications in the design of Digital Educational Escape rooms. *Journal of e-Learning and Knowledge Society* (May 2023), 67–74 Pages. doi:10.20368/1971-8829/1135749
- [165] Panshul Sharma, Jovern Teo, Mattias Wei Ren Kon, Jia Yi Han, and Fun Man Fung. 2025. ChemPOV: Evaluating a digital game-based learning tool for organic chemistry through student-researcher collaboration. *Journal of Applied Learning & Teaching* 8, Special Issue 2 (Feb. 2025). doi:10.37074/jalt.2025.8.S2.4
- [166] Micah Stohlmann. 2021. Two modes of game-based learning for middle school mathematics. *Journal of Mathematics Education at Teachers College* 12, 2 (2021), 9–20.
- [167] University of Granada, Spain, mlina@ugr.es, Lina Higuera-Rodríguez, Marta Medina-García, University of Granada, Spain, martamega@ugr.es, M^a Del Mar García-Vita, University of Granada, Spain, margvita@ugr.es, Enriqueta Molina-Ruiz, and University of Granada, Spain, emolina@ugr.es. 2024. Initial Training in the Use of Didactic Game Strategies: What Do Practising Teachers Say? *International Journal of Instruction* 17, 2 (April 2024), 283–302. doi:10.29333/iji.2024.17.2.16a
- [168] Jacqueline Žammit. 2022. Is mobile game-based learning effective for international adults learning Maltese? *Asian-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education* 7, 1 (Nov. 2022), 29. doi:10.1186/s40862-022-00157-2
- [172] Nikki Squire. 2023. Comparative Study of Game-based e-Pedagogies in an Online Undergraduate Course. *The Journal of Educators Online* 20, 1 (Jan. 2023). doi:10.9743/JEO.2023.20.1.13
- [173] Jie Zhang and Zijing Hu. 2024. Advancing game-based learning in higher education through debriefing: Social constructivism theory. *Journal for the Education of Gifted Young Scientists* 12, 1 (March 2024), 15–27. doi:10.17478/jegys.1394242
- [174] Omar Alawajee. 2021. Influence of COVID-19 on Students' Sign Language Learning in a Teacher-Preparation Program in Saudi Arabia: Moving to E-Learning. *Contemporary Educational Technology* 13, 3 (May 2021), ep308. doi:10.30935/cedtech/10886
- [175] Daniel Elford, Simon J. Lancaster, and Garth A. Jones. 2022. Exploring the Effect of Augmented Reality on Cognitive Load, Attitude, Spatial Ability, and Stereochemical Perception. *Journal of Science Education and Technology* 31, 3 (June 2022), 322–339. doi:10.1007/s10956-022-09957-0
- [176] Burhan Hamadneh, Amr Fikry, Mohammed Talaat, Ahmed Abbas, Reham Ghanem, Samah Ramzy, Mohamed Aly, Ahmed Elkilani, Sherin Mabrouk, and Reema Aloqlah. 2025. Exploring university students' perceptions and engagement in game-based learning. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)* 14, 1 (Feb. 2025), 525. doi:10.11591/ijere.v14i1.30494
- [177] Michael Pajor, Nicholas Xie, and Gregory Podolej. 2023. Medical student education simulation competitions. *The Clinical Teacher* 20, 1 (Feb. 2023), e13547. doi:10.1111/tct.13547
- [178] Elton L. Sciffes, Marcus Cox, Robert M. Crocker, Rajat Mishra, and Gerald W. Scott. 2021. Academic motivation and the undergraduate business major. *Journal of Education for Business* 96, 8 (Nov. 2021), 510–515. doi:10.1080/08832323.2020.1869680
- [179] Dusanka Slijepcevic, Biserka Kosarac, Aleksandra Hadzic, Branko Crnogorac, Ivan Sijakovic, Ewa Dabrowskapropkowska, and Braco Kovacevic. 2021. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF GAMES, AS A PRACTICE, FOR EDUCATION: STUDENTS' MOTIVATION FOR GAMING AND TENDENCY TO GAMES. Bucharest, RO, 569–578. doi:10.12753/2066-026X-21-072
- [180] Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Muhammad Amirul Kamarudin, Jameel Abdulla Ahmed Mukred, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Sri Sumarwati, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Nurhanim Saadah Abdullah, and Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia. 2023. Game Application as Teaching Tool to Assist Mastering Installation of Three-Phase Motor Control Topic: Expert Perception. *Online Journal for TVET Practitioners* 8, 3 (Nov. 2023). doi:10.30880/ojtp.2023.08.03.016

Papers Excluded - Missing Methodology

- [174] Omar Alawajee. 2021. Influence of COVID-19 on Students' Sign Language Learning in a Teacher-Preparation Program in Saudi Arabia: Moving to E-Learning. *Contemporary Educational Technology* 13, 3 (May 2021), ep308. doi:10.30935/cedtech/10886
- [175] Daniel Elford, Simon J. Lancaster, and Garth A. Jones. 2022. Exploring the Effect of Augmented Reality on Cognitive Load, Attitude, Spatial Ability, and Stereochemical Perception. *Journal of Science Education and Technology* 31, 3 (June 2022), 322–339. doi:10.1007/s10956-022-09957-0
- [176] Burhan Hamadneh, Amr Fikry, Mohammed Talaat, Ahmed Abbas, Reham Ghanem, Samah Ramzy, Mohamed Aly, Ahmed Elkilani, Sherin Mabrouk, and Reema Aloqlah. 2025. Exploring university students' perceptions and engagement in game-based learning. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)* 14, 1 (Feb. 2025), 525. doi:10.11591/ijere.v14i1.30494
- [177] Michael Pajor, Nicholas Xie, and Gregory Podolej. 2023. Medical student education simulation competitions. *The Clinical Teacher* 20, 1 (Feb. 2023), e13547. doi:10.1111/tct.13547
- [178] Elton L. Sciffes, Marcus Cox, Robert M. Crocker, Rajat Mishra, and Gerald W. Scott. 2021. Academic motivation and the undergraduate business major. *Journal of Education for Business* 96, 8 (Nov. 2021), 510–515. doi:10.1080/08832323.2020.1869680
- [179] Dusanka Slijepcevic, Biserka Kosarac, Aleksandra Hadzic, Branko Crnogorac, Ivan Sijakovic, Ewa Dabrowskapropkowska, and Braco Kovacevic. 2021. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF GAMES, AS A PRACTICE, FOR EDUCATION: STUDENTS' MOTIVATION FOR GAMING AND TENDENCY TO GAMES. Bucharest, RO, 569–578. doi:10.12753/2066-026X-21-072
- [180] Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Muhammad Amirul Kamarudin, Jameel Abdulla Ahmed Mukred, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Sri Sumarwati, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Nurhanim Saadah Abdullah, and Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia. 2023. Game Application as Teaching Tool to Assist Mastering Installation of Three-Phase Motor Control Topic: Expert Perception. *Online Journal for TVET Practitioners* 8, 3 (Nov. 2023). doi:10.30880/ojtp.2023.08.03.016

Papers Excluded - Other

- [181] Sandra Elsom, Marguerite Westacott, Colleen Stieler-Hunt, Sarah Glencross, and Kerry Rutter. 2023. Finding resources, finding friends: using an alternate reality game for orientation and socialisation in a university enabling program. *Interactive Learning Environments* 31, 5 (July 2023), 2635–2649. doi:10.1080/10494820.2021.1894181
- [182] Beaumie Kim, Reyhaneh Bastani, and Diali Gupta. 2024. Transforming teachers' self-narratives about game-based learning. *Educational technology research and development* 72, 2 (April 2024), 1225–1248. doi:10.1007/s11423-023-10319-9
- [183] Nina McLain, Mary Jane Collins, and LaWanda Baskin. 2023. Active Learning Methodologies in a High Stakes Graduate Nursing Program. *International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning* 17, 1 (2023), 1–9. doi:10.20429/ijstl.2023.17120

Received 28.11.2025; revised 19 December 2025; accepted 12 January 2026

Papers Excluded - No specific Discipline

- [169] Lea C. Brandl and Andreas Schrader. 2025. Realizing Ambient Serious Games in Higher Education—Concept and Heuristic Evaluation. *Trends in Higher Education* 4, 3 (Sept. 2025), 52. doi:10.3390/higheredu4030052
- [170] Benjamin Emihovich. 2024. Game-Based Learning and Systems Thinking: an Innovative Instructional Approach for the 21st Century. *TechTrends* 68, 1 (Jan. 2024), 174–185. doi:10.1007/s11528-023-00915-0
- [171] Kamal Omari. 2023. Towards an Intelligent Model for Evaluating Serious Games. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)* 18, 15 (Aug. 2023), 79–93. doi:10.3991/ijet.v18i15.40957